

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ASSESSMENTS OF PERSONNEL MANAGEMENT IN MODERN ECONOMIC CONDITIONS

Karimov K.

*associate professor, Azerbaijan State University of Oil and Industry,
International qualified economist*

Safarli Z.H.,

assistant, Azerbaijan State University of Oil and Industry,

Babirzade E.U.,

master student, Azerbaijan State University of Oil and Industry

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Abstract

The article discusses that assessing the effectiveness of the personnel management system of organizations is very important and relevant from the point of view of developing the functional potential of the organizations themselves in the development of integrated production management systems in the field of economics of the entire economy. The main methods for assessing efficiency in the personnel management system are analyzed in order to develop the functional potential of the organizations themselves in the development of integrated production management systems. According to the results of the study, it was revealed that human capital is becoming one of the decisive intangible factors of competitiveness of both the country as a whole and an individual enterprise. For this reason, it is urgent to improve the efficiency of the personnel management system in the new economy. Existing approaches and methods for assessing the effectiveness of the personnel management system are analyzed, their shortcomings and limitations are identified. It is concluded that it is necessary to use a new approach to personnel management in response to changes that have occurred in the management object itself.

Keywords: *personnel management, personnel management system, assessment of the influence of management system factors, management methods.*

INTRODUCTION

In modern conditions, personnel evaluation is a process that allows determining the activity of the employee as a whole and his suitability for the position he holds. Today, Azerbaijani and foreign scientists: G. Abdullayeva, B. Imanova, T. Guliyev, K. Shahbazov K, F. Gasimov, S. Mehbaliyev, as well as foreign scientists R. Beatty, B. Becker, E. Grove, G. Kelce, D. Cooper, T.Y. Bazarov, A. Kibanov, V.A. Dyatlov, G.Kh. Popov, I. Durakova, A.P. In the published scientific works of Egoshin, V. Vesnin, and others, there are several different interpretations of the concept of "personnel evaluation", that is, terms such as "personnel business assessment", "personnel certification", "personnel assessment". Thus, G. Abdullayeva characterizes the "business evaluation of personnel" as determining the quality characteristics of the person or the compliance with the requirements of the workplace.

V. Vesnin and I. Durakova considers the concepts of "personnel evaluation" and "certification" to be the same, and has generalized this phenomenon into a system of interrelated organizational processes and actions, an evaluation cycle that includes four elements of the degree of expression of certain qualities in employees and their compliance with the organization's requirements. This includes determining the required level of work tasks and their implementation by defining labor standards, goals, behavior standards, measuring and evaluating activities, feedback on the work done, improvement opportunities and directions, in other subsystems of the human resources management

system (payroll systems, personnel development, personnel recruitment and selection) interpret performance evaluation data for use.

It should be noted that there are many different methods for evaluating the personnel of an organization. All of them are based on the following principles: objectivity; reliability; reliability in relation to activities; presence of complexity.

The implementation of assessment measures should not only not disrupt the work of the organization, but also be included in the general system of personnel work in the organization in such a way as to actually contribute to its development and improvement. Considering the personnel evaluation methods, many experts divide them into two groups: traditional and non-traditional.

Traditional methods include testing, surveying and rating. Unconventional methods of personnel evaluation include the solution situation evaluation method, ABC-personnel analysis method, 360-degree evaluation method, evaluation center, competency evaluation, calligraphic handwriting method, and so on [1,2].

The calligraphy handwriting method is used to assess an employee's strengths and weaknesses based on his handwriting. The strengths of an employee with calligraphy are: responsibility, quality orientation, focus on results, tactical planning and process organization, problem analysis. Weaknesses include a low level or lack of: adaptability, positive thinking, flexibility and spontaneity, innovative and commercial thinking, systematic thinking (the ability to distinguish the main from the secondary), initiative, courage, flexibility, leadership.

Different personnel evaluation methods allow the employer to determine the existing and potential capabilities of the personnel with maximum accuracy, to see the strengths and weaknesses of the management system and to form the evaluation model of his employees.

Approaches to the evaluation of personnel management.

Personnel performance evaluation in enterprises is a complex system for determining the characteristics of employees in order to help the head of the organization in making management decisions to increase the performance of those.

Appraisal is closely related to almost all major functions of human resource management. So, these functions allow solving the following problems:

- Human resource planning: the evaluation of performance indicators determines the company's qualitative and quantitative human resource needs.
- Recruitment: evaluation shows how effective the methods of attracting and selecting new employees are used in the company.
- Staff training: Assessment identifies training needs and determines the effectiveness of existing training programs.
- Formation of personnel stock: it is based on the assessment of the work and work behavior of the company's employees.
- Analysis of personnel performance: evaluation allows to determine the standards and indicators by which the work behavior of the employees of a particular company is evaluated.
- Personnel development: assessment reveals the work potential of employees.
- Financial incentive system: evaluation increases the effectiveness of motivational systems.

The main objectives of the above are to determine the relationship between the costs of retaining an employee and the amount of work he actually performs, to assess the potential of existing employees and to determine the functional role of each employee [3,4,8].

Ultimately, the measures taken have a positive effect on the performance of individual employees and the company as a whole. For example, personnel evaluation in Japan is based on determining the capabilities of each individual employee in accordance with the country's production philosophy. Today, Azerbaijani companies are actively revising their approach to personnel evaluation. At the same time, managers and employees of the personnel department, who are not experienced enough in comparison to the evaluation methods widely used abroad, face difficulties in their

application. Unfortunately, neither in Azerbaijan nor in the literature and scientific researches related to the management of foreign companies, there is still no single system for solving all the problems that have arisen. To minimize these difficulties, it is necessary to involve qualified consultants who will help explain the necessity of the procedure, prepare and implement it [5,6].

Evaluation criteria and methods of personnel management in current conditions.

It is about the work, personal, behavioral and other characteristics by which the employee's performance is evaluated. Each criterion defines how a job function should be performed to fully meet customer and company requirements. When preparing personnel evaluation criteria, it is necessary to take into account the characteristics of the organization's activity, the market segment in which it operates, the goals and objectives of the evaluation, that is, what is planned to be obtained from it. It is also necessary to determine which criteria will be preferred. For example, when evaluating personnel, the main criterion may be the quality of work. The main requirements for a set of criteria: accessibility, objectivity, transparency, relevance to the content of the work, employee motivation and dynamism to achieve results. the ability to develop according to the current changes occurring in the company.

All personnel evaluation criteria can be divided into two groups:

1. Assessment of skills. At this time, the employee's knowledge and skills, ability to apply them in practical work, as well as behavior and personal qualities are evaluated. One of the most effective ways to assess skills is to solve situational problems, taking into account the characteristics of the position that the employee holds or plans to hold.

2. Performance evaluation. It is based on the comparison of performance indicators of a certain employee with the indicators planned for a certain work period and position. For this, clear measurable objectives must be set before the evaluation begins. Employee performance can be expressed, for example, by monthly sales volume, number of completed projects, amount of profit, or number of closed transactions [7,10].

The preparation of evaluation criteria is carried out by specialists together with the managers or employees who perform the relevant work. This is necessary so that the criteria are clear to all participants of the evaluation and take into account the specific conditions and content of the work (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Model of personnel management methods

It is clear from Figure 1 that there are many approaches to personnel evaluation, which can be explained as follows:

Questionnaire. A questionnaire is filled out with a certain set of questions, after which the absence or presence of these traits is analyzed.

Descriptive assessment. The evaluator identifies and describes negative and positive behavioral traits of the person being assessed. It is often used as a complement to other methods, since it does not provide for recording the results.

Classification. It is based on ranking those assessed according to a certain criterion from best to worst, and they are assigned certain serial numbers.

Comparison by pairs. A pairwise comparison of candidates in the same position is performed, after which the number of times the person being assessed was the best in the pair is counted. Then, based on the results obtained, an overall group rating is compiled.

Rating. Based on an assessment of the employee's suitability for the position held. It is a scaling of personal qualities of personnel, in which the most important component is a list of the employee's functions. After its preparation, the work is studied taking into account the time spent on it. In addition, it also takes into account whether the employee uses material resources economically. Next, the qualities are assessed on a seven-point scale, where 7 is a very high degree, and 1 is a very low degree. The results can be assessed by the correspondence of the identified qualities to the reference ones, or in comparison with the results of other employees occupying the same position as the subject.

Critical Situation Assessment. Before using this method of personnel assessment, a list of descriptions of the "wrong" and "correct" behavior of employees in typical ("decisive") situations is prepared. Further, in accordance with the nature of the work, these descriptions are distributed according to headings. After this, the evaluator prepares a special journal in which he records examples of the behavior of each employee being

evaluated for each rubric. Subsequently, this magazine is used as a basic criterion for assessing business qualities.

"360 degrees". This method of personnel assessment involves evaluating an employee not only by his immediate supervisor, but by colleagues and subordinates. The specific forms of this type of assessment may differ, but its meaning is that all assessors must fill out the same forms, after which the results are processed using a computer to ensure anonymity. The purpose of this method is to obtain comprehensive, objective assessment results.

According to this, the HR manager needs to conduct employee assessments at the enterprise. When choosing personnel assessment methods, you must clearly know its goals: assessing the performance of employees and their suitability for their positions, as well as identifying promising employees for promotion. Thus, the procedure for selecting and assessing personnel is divided into two components: labor assessment; personnel assessment.

Labor assessment is necessary to compare the actual content, quality, volume and intensity of employee work with the planned ones.

Personnel assessment is necessary to: study the degree of preparedness of a person to perform exactly the work that is entrusted to him; identifying the level of potential opportunities in order to assess growth prospects; developing personnel activities that are necessary to achieve the goals of the personnel strategy. As practice shows, in most cases, organizations use both types simultaneously. It should also be noted that the immediate superiors of those being assessed, other managers, colleagues, subordinates, external consultants and the person being assessed can be involved in the assessment of work (self-assessment) [9,11].

One of the personnel evaluation methods is Key Performance Indicators (KPI). This method is a personnel evaluation system that allows determining the effectiveness of the company's employees in terms of

their ability to achieve strategic and tactical goals. The KPI system refers to meritocratic methods, that is, approaches based on work evaluation based on real achievements using objective measurement mechanisms [12].

The KPI evaluation methodology assumes that two models (in tabular form) of current results and competencies are developed for each position in the company. First, it lists all the criteria by which the employee's performance should be evaluated - quantity and quality, team and individual. Second, the competencies required for this position are corporate, managerial and expert. In order to evaluate the results of an employee's competence for a certain period, five to seven main indicators are selected from two models and recorded in his personal activity table. In this case, powers are equal to the quality results of his work. The employee's direct supervisor gives weight from 0 to 1 to each of the selected indicators. At the same time, he only focuses on his priorities. The total weight of indicators should be equal to one.

By the way:

- Base - the starting point from which the result is measured. Worst value.
- Norm - the level that should be achieved, taking into account all circumstances.
- Goal – a level to strive for, a sort of ideal benchmark.

At the end of the control period, all KPI indicators are evaluated. In this case, qualitative indicators are evaluated on an ordinal 100-point scale, and quantitative indicators are evaluated on a natural metric scale.

CONCLUSION

The modern system of personnel assessment of an organization is considered as a way of knowing the object. The development of a personnel assessment procedure should include the use of a variety of methods, techniques and means of achieving the set assessment goals using related fields of knowledge, such as statistics, psychology, sociology, etc. at different stages of the organization's personnel assessment. The choice of assessment tools is not subject to regulation, and depends on the goals, time, available information and other organizational resources.

Our research showed that there is still no precise definition of the essence of the concept of human resources development management in the works of domestic and foreign economists-scientists dedicated to the management of the human factor. From this point of view, analyzing the essence of the concepts mentioned above, it can be concluded that we offer a unique definition to the concepts of "personnel", "personnel development" and "personnel management". We believe that "human resources management" is a set of methods that serve to identify and reveal the hidden potential of an employee. The purpose of this process is to achieve the improvement of the quality characteristics of personnel, as well as the level of socio-economic development of enterprises. At the same time, the nature of human resources activity requires significant changes and its management, informatization of soci-

ety. Accordingly, the role of material production partially decreases and the importance of the service sphere increases. The mentioned processes make new requirements for the improvement of the qualification level of employees, especially the use of information bases and streams with a very wide scope becomes an important issue. Under these conditions, the effective management of human resources depends on the correct definition of the content of this economic concept.

Therefore, the adoption of correct and optimal management decisions largely depends on the correct and optimal organization of those stages, because, in our opinion, those stages, first of all, serve to achieve the strategic goals and tasks of personnel management.

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